

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4a)

Progress of Excavation 4a signalled as compact tan clay - fairly uniform, undulating under rubble, stones at (4). All sample containers, baskets changed. C. Zivic commences excavation (4a) Under darker tan clay¹⁵ band of lighter, clearer tan clay. In photo of surface of (4a) still bit of (4) adhering (4a) - still large to small limestone frags. // 4:00 PM. Lighter Tan band turns out to be lens in essentially same material as (4). Aside from sample of lens of light tan clay exclusively, this band cleared down into continuation of (4) type deposit to within

Locus Description Compact concentrated tan clay 20-30 cm bedrock floor. OVER-
DARK TAN CLAY - gray mud spots
Carbon flecks (occasional), few limestone frags

Location in Square NE corner, rounding of (4), etc

Under Locus (4) Buff Sand Stone Rubble Over Locus (4b) LIGHT BUFF CLAY-GYPSUM

Locus Dimensions 2-4 cm. thick

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

10/I/80: CLEAR THAT under ④ there is a thin but uniform band of dark tan compact clay and this is properly ④a. Under this is much lighter buff gypsum-clay mix ④b 3-6 cm thick, then under this to bedrock ④c which is much like ④

④a DARK TAN CLAY sampled separately today.